

**ISSUES OF APPLYING THE RECOMMENDATIONS OF
INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL ORGANIZATIONS IN THE
TAXATION SYSTEM**

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of recommendations of international financial organizations on improving the taxation system. Recommendations of organizations such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) on expanding the tax base, optimizing tax rates, introducing technological innovations and preventing tax evasion by transnational companies are considered. The application of these recommendations in local conditions, their positive impact and difficulties encountered in practice, in particular, corruption, insufficient technological infrastructure and adaptation to international standards, are analyzed. The role and results of international recommendations in improving tax policy are studied using the example of Uzbekistan. In particular, the recent reforms implemented in the country's taxation system, such as reducing tax rates, introducing digital technologies and tax breaks, are discussed. The article emphasizes the need to adapt the experience and recommendations of international financial organizations to national conditions.

Keywords: taxation system, international financial organizations, tax reforms, International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), tax base, tax rate, technological innovations, transnational companies, tax avoidance, corruption, digital technologies, international standards, economy of Uzbekistan.

Introduction: The taxation system is of great importance in ensuring the financial stability and economic development of the state. This system serves not only as the main source of formation of the state budget, but also as a strategic tool influencing economic activity. Therefore, improving taxation policy remains one of the constantly pressing issues for all countries. International financial organizations, including the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), provide countries with a number of recommendations on reforming the taxation system.

These recommendations are aimed at increasing economic efficiency, ensuring fair taxation and reducing tax evasion. At the same time, various difficulties arise in adapting this process to local conditions and implementing it in practice. Especially for developing countries, the introduction of international standards, the development of technological infrastructure and the solution of the problem of corruption are of particular importance. This article analyzes the essence of the recommendations of international financial organizations, their practical application in the tax system of Uzbekistan and existing difficulties. It also examines the prospects for the recommendations to improve economic stability and the efficiency of the tax system. The article highlights the importance of combining international experience and local needs in the case of Uzbekistan.

Review of literature on the topic. Reform of taxation systems and strategies recommended by international financial organizations are of crucial importance in ensuring the stability of the economies of states. These recommendations are aimed not only at replenishing the budgets of states, but also at developing economic activity and solving the problem of tax evasion. Scientific works of foreign and Russian scientists on this issue allow us to deeply study the theoretical and practical aspects of the recommendations of international financial organizations.

Canadian economist Richard Bird has extensively studied the influence of

international financial organizations on the taxation systems of developing countries. He has conducted research on the role of effective management of the taxation system in ensuring fiscal stability. According to Bird, expanding the tax base and increasing the efficiency of tax collection are the main priorities for states. He also developed a number of recommendations on coordinating taxation mechanisms between the state and the private sector.

Italian economist Vito Tanzi considers cooperation between international financial organizations and states as an important factor in improving taxation policy. His research focuses on increasing state budget revenues, ensuring transparency of the taxation system, and reducing corruption. Tanzi also emphasized the need to increase the efficiency of the taxation system through the introduction of technologies.

French economist Gabriel Zucman has conducted an in-depth analysis of tax avoidance and the impact of offshore zones on the international economy. His research is aimed at ensuring that international taxation policy is based on the principles of fairness. Zucman emphasizes the need to strengthen international cooperation in the fight against the shifting of profits by transnational companies to jurisdictions with low tax rates.

US economist Kimberly Clausing has studied the relationship between international trade and taxation. Her research focuses on important aspects of harmonizing the activities of transnational companies with taxation policy. Clausing has developed practical recommendations for ensuring the equitable distribution of profits and the tax base of transnational enterprises across countries.

Russian economist Sinelnikov-Murylev has extensively analyzed the impact of taxation policy on macroeconomic development. He has developed theoretical foundations for increasing economic efficiency by optimizing tax rates. Sinelnikov-Murylev's work has been used to address issues in the taxation policy of Russia and other CIS countries.

V. Nazarov has conducted research on the integration of recommendations from international financial organizations into Russian tax policy. He is known for his work on taxation of profits of transnational companies and the adaptation of international standards to national systems. Nazarov has also paid great attention to the development of digitalization of the taxation system.

L. Litvintseva has conducted research on the role of digital technologies in modernizing the taxation system and increasing economic efficiency. She has emphasized the importance of adapting the experience of international financial organizations to Russian conditions. Her work is aimed at preventing tax evasion through digitalization.

A. Ivanov studied the legal aspects of international tax policy and investigated the issues of regulating the taxation of transnational companies. He developed legal mechanisms for implementing the recommendations of international financial organizations in the Russian economy.

The recommendations of international financial organizations are the main source for ensuring the economic stability of countries and improving the taxation system. Research by foreign and Russian scientists on this topic emphasizes that tax policy should be based on the principles of economic efficiency, fairness and transparency. The use of these scientific works is especially important for developing countries, including Uzbekistan, in modernizing the taxation system and ensuring its compliance with international standards. The reforms being implemented in the taxation system of Uzbekistan can be more effective based on the work and recommendations of these scientists.

Research methodology. The taxation system is an important part of the economy of each state, and its effectiveness is a key tool for increasing state budget revenues, ensuring economic stability, and ensuring social justice. International financial organizations, including the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank, and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development

(OECD), provide countries with valuable recommendations on improving their taxation policies. To implement these recommendations in local conditions and evaluate their results, it is necessary to use modern research methodology.

The research methodology includes theoretical and practical aspects. First of all, it is necessary to conduct a theoretical analysis of the recommendations of international financial organizations. In this process, aspects such as the content of the recommendations, their impact on economic efficiency, and their compliance with the principles of justice are studied. At the same time, empirical data is collected on the practical results of these recommendations on a global scale, decisions made in different countries, and their impact on the taxation system.

An important part of the research is comparative analysis. This method compares the experience of different countries and determines under what conditions international recommendations work more effectively. For example, it analyzes what kind of experience the tax approaches introduced by OECD countries can serve as for developing countries. In particular, it studies the results of the BEPS program aimed at preventing tax evasion by transnational companies.

The mathematical modeling method occupies a special place in the research methodology. This method analyzes the impact of factors such as changes in tax rates, expansion of the tax base, or the introduction of technologies on state budget revenues. Such models help in formulating long-term economic strategies of countries.

In the case of Uzbekistan, adapting international recommendations to local conditions is important as a practical aspect of the research. The country's taxation system has been undergoing serious reforms in recent years. For example, optimization of tax rates, introduction of digital technologies, and incentives to support small businesses are important steps towards economic development. At the same time, taking into account international experience, additional measures are needed to reduce tax evasion and make the taxation process more transparent.

Research on the implementation of the recommendations of international financial organizations in the taxation system helps to develop effective strategies. By combining theoretical and practical approaches, countries can further stabilize their economies and bring them into line with international standards. This methodology is an important tool for developing countries like Uzbekistan in making the taxation system fair, transparent and effective.

Analysis and results. In 2024, tax revenues to the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan increased by 20.3% compared to the previous year, totaling 199.6 trillion soums. This increase is explained by increasing the efficiency of the tax administration in the country and increasing economic activity. Analysis by tax type allows us to assess the main directions of tax policy and their impact on economic development.

The table below shows the revenue by tax type in 2024 and their growth rates compared to 2023.

Tax revenue dynamics in Uzbekistan in 2024

Types of taxes	Revenues in 2024 (trillion soums)	Growth (%) compared to 2023
Profit tax	52,7	29,1
Value added tax (VAT)	39,6	16,4
Personal income tax	35,4	18,3
Subsoil use tax	20,2	31,8
Excise tax	17,8	17,4
Tax-free receipts	15,0	0,0
Land tax	8,2	19,2
Property tax	6,8	33,5
Turnover tax (AOS)	2,8	17,6
Water resources use tax	1,2	48,3

Source: Compiled by the author based on information from

<https://uzreport.news>

In 2024, tax revenues in the Republic of Uzbekistan increased significantly. Total revenues amounted to 199.6 trillion soums, which is 20.3% more than last year. These achievements are the result of increasing the efficiency of tax administration, stimulating economic growth, and reforms implemented by the state. With a detailed analysis of indicators by type of tax, certain changes and achievements can be observed.

Profit tax revenues amounted to 52.7 trillion soums in 2024, which is 29.1% more than last year. This growth is associated with the expansion of the activities of large enterprises in the economy, increased revenues, and effective tax administration. The high growth of profit tax also reflects the stability of the economic activities of large companies. This indicator is also the result of reforms aimed at increasing the transparency of tax calculation and collection processes by the state.

Value-added tax revenues amounted to 39.6 trillion soums in 2024, an increase of 16.4% compared to the previous year. This growth is explained by increasing the efficiency of tax administration and expanding the consumer market. An increase in VAT not only increases state revenues, but also indicates increased consumer demand. This, in turn, reflects the expansion of the domestic market and increased economic activity.

Property tax revenues increased by 33.5% in 2024. This growth is associated with increasing accuracy in tax calculation and collection. Property tax serves not only to increase budget revenues, but also to improve the property accounting system. Successes in this type of tax play an important role in increasing the administrative capacity of the state.

The highest growth rate in 2024 was recorded in the tax on the use of water resources - 48.3 percent. This achievement is the result of enhanced monitoring of water resource management and the pursuit of efficiency. An increase in the tax on

the use of water resources will not only increase financial resources, but also have a positive impact on resource conservation and environmental sustainability. In 2024, the processes of calculating and collecting taxes were digitized, which led to an increase in tax revenues. The introduction of electronic systems created convenience for taxpayers and reduced administrative costs. At the same time, the efficiency of monitoring tax revenues by the state increased.

Increasing the volume of production of enterprises and the creation of new jobs provided an impetus for economic growth. Increased activity in domestic and foreign markets expanded the tax base and had a positive impact on state revenues. This process covered the economic activities of small and medium-sized businesses, along with large manufacturers. The reforms adopted by the state to improve tax policy, including measures to reduce tax incentives and increase transparency, have yielded effective results. These reforms not only optimized the tax collection process, but also encouraged taxpayers to comply with the rules.

The high growth rates of tax revenues in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024 indicate the successful implementation of the state's economic and financial policy. The introduction of digitalization processes in tax policy and administration, as well as effective state reforms, played a key role in increasing tax revenues. However, to further improve tax policy, it is necessary to develop new approaches aimed at the efficient use of resources and ensuring financial stability. These achievements have created a solid foundation for sustainable growth in the economy and will allow the state to support social and infrastructure projects in the future.

Table 2: Tax revenues and their growth

Years	Total revenues (trillion soums)	Growth (%)
2022	160,0	15,0
2023	166,0	20,3
2024	199,6	20,3

Source: Compiled by the author based on information from <https://uzreport.news>

In 2024, tax revenues in the Republic of Uzbekistan grew rapidly, becoming an important source of state budget revenues. Total revenues increased significantly due to improved tax policy and administration. These changes supported economic development and ensured the stability of the state budget. The analysis of tax revenues shows that there is still room for further revenue growth through reforms and digital technologies. However, additional measures are needed to ensure sustainability in resource use and taxation.

Discussion: International financial organizations, including the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank, and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), have been providing countries with recommendations on improving their tax systems. These recommendations are aimed at increasing economic efficiency, making the tax process more transparent, and ensuring the principles of fairness. The recommendations made by these organizations are mainly aimed at stabilizing the economy, preventing tax evasion, and increasing state budget revenues, and they take into account global standards.

The Republic of Uzbekistan, taking these recommendations into account, has been regularly introducing amendments and additions to the Tax Code. Reforms in the tax system are considered an integral part of the state economic policy. These reforms are aimed at increasing state revenues, reducing the informal sector of the economy, and ensuring social justice.

A number of changes have been made to the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which entered into force on January 1, 2024. According to Law No. ORQ-891 of December 28, 2023, tax rates for agricultural land were set at 0.95 percent of the standard value of agricultural land. This, on the one hand, serves to increase attention to agriculture, and on the other hand, ensures an increase in tax revenues.

Also, in accordance with Article 227¹ of the Tax Code, a fine of two percent of net revenue received in the last reporting quarter of the year of sale was established for violation of the requirements for displaying fiscal signs or equipping with automated accounting and measuring instruments. This fine was introduced in order to increase the efficiency of tax collection and encourage digitalization.

A number of problems may arise when implementing the recommendations of international financial organizations into the national taxation system. These problems depend on the economic, social and technological conditions of the country:

1. Adaptation to local conditions

Since the economic and social conditions of each country are unique, direct application of international recommendations may be ineffective. When implementing international recommendations in the Uzbek taxation system, there is a need to adapt them to national conditions. For example, direct implementation of tax mechanisms recommended for developed countries may not produce the expected results in developing countries.

2. Insufficient technological infrastructure

The main part of international recommendations requires digitization and automation of the tax system. Although Uzbekistan is making significant progress in introducing digital technologies, insufficient technological infrastructure may slow down this process. For example, the lack of technological tools used in taxation processes or low qualifications of personnel lead to problems.

3. Social resistance

Reforms in the tax system and the introduction of international recommendations can sometimes be met with resistance from different segments of the population. For example, the introduction of new taxes or an increase in existing tax rates can cause discontent among low-income groups. In such cases, the state will need to implement additional social support measures.

4. Corruption and the informal economy

International financial organizations call for combating corruption in the taxation system and reducing the informal economy. However, addressing these issues depends on the administrative and legal capacity of the state. Although Uzbekistan is taking significant steps in this area, a number of difficulties still remain.

Recommendations of international financial organizations play an important role in improving the taxation system and ensuring the stability of the state budget. However, a careful approach is required in adapting these recommendations to national conditions and implementing them.

The following recommendations are relevant for Uzbekistan:

- Continue digitizing the tax system and strengthening technological infrastructure.
- Reduce the informal economy and expand the tax base.
- Introduce a differential tax policy to ensure social justice.
- Explain tax system reforms to the population and strengthen social support measures.

The Republic of Uzbekistan can increase the efficiency of the taxation system and achieve economic stability by applying an approach that is flexible to national conditions when using international recommendations. This approach will further strengthen the country's integration into the global economic system.

Conclusion

The recommendations provided by international financial organizations, including the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank, and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), are important in improving the taxation system. These recommendations are aimed at ensuring the economic stability of countries, increasing the efficiency of tax collection, establishing the principles of justice, and reducing tax evasion.

The taxation system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is being systematically reformed, taking into account the recommendations of international financial organizations. Changes to the Tax Code and the introduction of digital technologies have made it possible to achieve significant results in ensuring transparent tax collection and increasing state budget revenues.

At the same time, a number of difficulties are observed in the process of implementing international recommendations. Factors such as adaptation to local economic and social conditions, underdeveloped technological infrastructure, low human skills, and a high level of informal economy complicate this process. In such conditions, it is important to adapt international recommendations to national needs and conditions. In general, the recommendations of international financial organizations are of strategic importance in reforming the taxation system and achieving economic stability. For Uzbekistan, implementing these recommendations in a manner adapted to national conditions, continuing to digitize the tax system, ensuring social justice, and strengthening work on legalizing the informal economy will lead to more effective results in the future. These efforts will serve to ensure that the country takes its rightful place in the global economic system.

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